

VEGEST: Towards Fully Open and Reproducible TEI Workflows

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1 Introduction

The *Text Encoding Initiative* (TEI) defines text-encoding guidelines that are widely used in the humanities, and they also maintain computer programs to work with these

guidelines.¹ This paper discusses issues of reproducibility that arise in workflows that use texts encoded according to the TEI's guidelines. The discussion is informed by an ongoing effort to establish a framework for TEI/XML workflows at a research institute that specialises in the production of scholarly editions of pre-modern Sanskrit and Tibetan works. Even though many of the planned workflows have not been implemented yet, the general principles of the framework have been established. The conclusions drawn here should be useful to anyone who has to plan TEI/XML workflows for a diverse group of projects, as well as for scholars who are unable to cover all aspects of such workflows by themselves.

After this introduction, which adds details about the specific situation at the institute in question, there follows an overview of the state of the art of TEI/XML workflows in similar settings (section 2). In section 3, some typical problems are examined, leading to questions about some assumptions underlying the current best practices. There follows (section 4) an introduction of the framework provided by the *Vienna Encoding Guidelines for Editing Sanskrit Texts* (the VEGEST, for short) and a discussion of the attempt to avoid some of the reproducibility problems that the previous section identified in common TEI/XML workflows.² This section also contains some practical examples that show how the methods proposed to ensure long-term reproducibility can be applied to some common tasks in TEI workflows.

Institutional setting The Institute for the Cultural and Intellectual History of Asia (IKGA for short, <https://www.oeaw.ac.at/ikga/>) belongs to the Austrian Academy of Sciences. As such, it is a research institute that does not offer academic degrees. At any given time over the last decade, there have been approximately twenty-five researchers active at the Institute, distributed across four research areas: Buddhist studies, Indology, Tibetan studies and East Asian studies. One area of specialisation of scholars at the IKGA is the production of editions of Buddhist Sanskrit texts.³ These texts, typically authored between the fourth and thirteenth centuries CE, often belong to the genre of Buddhist philosophy. The editorial projects producing these editions have diverse settings: some are temporally limited, third-party funded endeavours, either by senior scholars who can make all expert editorial decisions themselves, or by junior

¹See TEI P5 Guidelines and TEI XSLT. The README.md of TEI P5 Guidelines states: "The TEI is international and interdisciplinary standard used by libraries, museums, publishers, and academics to represent all kinds of literary and linguistic texts, using an encoding scheme that is maximally expressive and minimally obsolescent."

²Throughout this paper, I refer to a "VEGEST framework" that consists of VEGEST schemas and VEGEST library at the versions specified in the references.

³Some of these works are published in the series *Sanskrit Texts From the Tibetan Autonomous Region (STTAR)*. See <https://www.oeaw.ac.at/en/ikga/publications/series/sanskrit-texts-from-the-tibetan-autonomous-region-sttar> and <https://verlag.oeaw.ac.at/reihe/sanskrit-texts-from-the-tibetan-autonomous-region/100>.

scholars or PhD candidates who might require some guidance; other projects are run by core members of the IKGA, often for works that are too large to be edited by a single scholar or in a third-party funded project; and there are also co-operations with scholars or groups of scholars wholly outside the institute, e.g. for Jinendrabuddhi’s *Pramāṇasamuccayaṭīkā* (see Steinkellner, Krasser, and Lasic 2005 for the first of six chapters).

For all scholars involved, the editorial project has to end in a printed edition—diplomatic, critical or, preferably, both. The reason for this is mostly a practical one: in the academic fields relevant for the careers of most of these scholars, the primary measure of success is a peer-reviewed publication in a traditional book format.

The framework that the VEGEST provides aims to support these diverse projects in the form of what I would like to call an “implemented adaptation of the TEI guidelines.”

2 Best practice in TEI projects, and VEGEST’s aim

Any TEI-based encoding project consists of a normative and a descriptive part. The normative aspect defines the machine-actionable rules that can be used to verify the conformance of any given document to the encoding rules of the project. Typically, these rules will be specified in a RelaxNG (Relax NG) schema. The descriptive part is the documentation of the encoding rules, adding to them prose definitions, examples of usage, further discussions and so on.

With the ODD format, short for “One Document Does it all”, the TEI P5 Guidelines: chapter 23 defines a type of TEI-XML file that makes it possible to derive the descriptive and the normative elements from the same document: in an ODD file, encoders can adapt the general TEI Guidelines to specific use cases and add documentation to suit project needs. An ODD processor then uses this single file to generate a formal schema, as well as formatted documentation.⁴

Even if TEI projects do not contain explicit documentation or schemas, one can posit that by the mere fact of using the TEI XML namespace (<http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0>) the encoded files purport to follow the rules of the TEI P5 Guidelines.

Many TEI projects also provide one or more processing mechanisms that operate on TEI-encoded documents. I will call this part the implementation because it is an abstract procedure encoded in one or more programming languages. In this sense, one can thus “implement” the transformation of a TEI document into a $\text{T}_{\text{E}}\text{X}$ file, or also a simple query that can be run on the files.

This article distinguishes TEI frameworks from individual TEI projects. While the

⁴See the sections “Documentation Elements,” “Customization,” and “Implementation of an ODD system” in TEI P5 Guidelines: §§22, 23.3, 23.5. The TEI Guidelines themselves use the ODD system described in those sections.

distinction is a gradual rather than a clear-cut one, “frameworks” can be thought of as customisations and applications of the general TEI Guidelines (TEI P5 Guidelines) that are intended to support multiple encoding projects. Individual encoding projects embed themselves within one or more frameworks.

Furthermore, frameworks can nest (or even overlap with) other frameworks. All TEI-conforming frameworks and individual projects should fit within the general TEI rules. This should not be taken to mean that each TEI document that validates against the rules of a particular TEI customisation will also validate against a more general set of rules. A TEI customisation can modify the content model of elements, permit attributes not permitted in the general TEI, and even introduce new elements. The distinction between frameworks and individual projects is a practical rather than a formal one.⁵

The VEGEST schemas qualify as a framework because they are designed for multiple and diverging individual projects. The VEGEST schemas select and sometimes redefine elements from vanilla TEI (TEI P5 Guidelines), while aiming at maximum compatibility. Wherever possible, the VEGEST schemas limit and restrict TEI rules to specific cases. Only in special cases do they alter the content model.⁶ What, then, are the frameworks that the VEGEST consider exemplary and try to emulate?

2.1 Exemplary TEI frameworks

This section discusses two widely used TEI frameworks that continue to serve as models to the VEGEST framework.⁷

⁵A different approach is to think of TEI-encoding projects as having only family resemblance to each other. Using roughly the same elements, defined in roughly the same way, makes these projects recognisably similar without positing any single feature that remains identical throughout all projects. Whether this approach suggests a change of XML namespaces for elements is debatable. In the XML-world, a change to the meaning of an element should usually result in the change of the XML namespace. This follows from the motivation for having XML namespaces (Bray et al. 2009: §1).

⁶Currently, VEGEST schemas does not add any new elements to TEI P5 Guidelines.

⁷There are of course several other TEI frameworks which are not discussed here. One important omission is TextGrid (see Zielinski et al. 2009). The reason the TextGrid framework was not evaluated here is that it is, in a sense, too wide in its scope. TextGrid requires conformity of documents to a baseline encoding, which is not sufficiently limited to the types of editions that the VEGEST framework targets. See TextGrid 2007–2009 for details, and the summary in Zielinski et al. 2009: 5.2:

A specific schema, called baseline encoding, is a key innovation in TextGrid developed together with other humanities computing projects encoding different varieties of text like dictionaries, drama, letters, critical editions, and language corpora. It has been designed in order to gain optimal retrieval performance across all TEI documents in TextGrid.

While the TEI P5 Guidelines are of course also extremely general, they do describe in detail the criteria of the editions that the VEGEST framework is intended for.

Other sources for the VEGEST schemas (though not frameworks themselves) include Balogh and Griffiths 2020 and Griffiths and Janiak 2023 (a new version of the latter is to appear soon).

2.1.1 The TEI Guidelines

At the risk of stating the obvious, the TEI Guidelines (here always TEI P5 Guidelines) are themselves a model to follow. They provide the most extensive TEI framework (in the sense just discussed), such that any other TEI framework or project is going to nest within or at least overlap with the categories defined in them. The TEI P5 Guidelines are themselves written in ODD documents and are recursive in that they define themselves: the ODD documents, together with the software provided by the TEI Consortium, produce the schemas that the ODD documents have to conform to. The documentation encoded in the ODD documents is converted to formats suitable for reading, such as HTML or PDF, through software and programs distributed by the TEI (see fig. 1).

Figure 1: Dependency of norms and documentation on computations (A,B) for an ODD-based TEI project

The generation of both the documentation and the schemas (or, the descriptive and normative elements of TEI projects) is a computational transformation of the ODD documents to a human-readable (HTML, PDF) and a schema format (typically Relax NG).⁸ Since the resulting schemas are text files, they can be stored alongside the ODD documents and tracked through the versioning system as well.

But tracking the input and output of a computation is not the same as making the results reproducible. Even in this situation involving only text files, results may still be irreproducible. The TEI Guidelines themselves assist projects in this situation. Since their source archive includes some of the programs to perform the computations (Jing, Saxon HE),⁹ one can add the TEI repositories (typically, TEI P5 Guidelines and TEI XSLT) to one's own and pin these added repositories to a specific version.¹⁰ This

⁸See section 2.1.2 for some details on the organisation of the individual content in the TEI and EpiDoc frameworks.

⁹These are distributed as Java Archives in https://github.com/TEIC/TEI/tree/P5_Release_4.9.0/P5/Utilities/lib.

¹⁰In Git, one can achieve this with submodules (see <https://git-scm.com/docs/>

approach enables the production of schema files from ODD documents at a specific version of the included repositories.¹¹

But there is a more fundamental issue that limits the reproducibility of the ODD→RNG transformation. Even if “some of the programs” are available from the TEI’s repositories, these programs always run in a particular computing environment. Professional software (such as that distributed in the TEI’s repositories) is very effective at mitigating this factor. The two programs mentioned are written in Java, and it is Java that ensures that their environment (at runtime) is stable enough to consistently produce the same results, regardless of a computer’s operating system, processor architecture, or available libraries. The fundamental problem is how much of the environment can change before the computer programs stop working. It is possible that they will run indefinitely, but the likelihood of their successful execution diminishes over time.¹²

2.1.2 EpiDoc

A well-known and widely used TEI framework is EpiDoc. The EpiDoc Website describes EpiDoc as “[...] an international, collaborative effort that provides guidelines and tools for encoding scholarly and educational editions of ancient documents.” It lists the core components of EpiDoc as follows (I quote):¹³

- EpiDoc Guidelines: recommendations for markup of transcription, descriptive features, etc. (About)
- EpiDoc Schema: the TEI-derived schema against which EpiDoc XML should be validated

`git-submodule`). A trivial example of this can be found in a repository maintained by the author that <https://github.com/paddymcall/teistuff>, where the official repositories of the TEI Guidelines and the TEI Stylesheets are traced as submodules.

¹¹Even in this situation, the results are not immediately reproducible for the trivial reason that the ODD→RNG transformation places a timestamp in the generated schemas. In VEGEST schemas we also track the resulting schema files, even though this is not strictly necessary once the transformation that produces them is reliably reproducible. But for practical reasons it is helpful to have them in place. If we had to reproduce them every time, we would always need to check out the TEI Stylesheets and the TEI Guidelines repositories, since they contain the main programs and rules to run the transformations.

¹²See Smithies et al. 2019 for an assessment of archiving DH projects. The TEI’s Docker environment (see footnote 32) specifies `openjdk-17-jdk-headless` as a software requirement for running the TEI’s programs. I was able to ascertain that `openjdk@23.0.2` still works, whereas version 24 results in an error message about a permanently disabled security manager. So, there are already versions of the Java (or rather, Red Hat’s OpenJDK) runtime environment that are incompatible with the TEI infrastructure. While this error is likely trivial to fix and OpenJDK is a model of long term support (see https://access.redhat.com/articles/1299013#OpenJDK_Life_Cycle, <2025-06-03 Tue>), the principal issue remains: one cannot guarantee that this workflow will remain functional for an extended period of time (in this case, probably decades).

¹³“EFES” is short for “EpiDoc Front Ende Services.” The source code is hosted at <https://github.com/EpiDoc/EFES>.

- EpiDoc Reference Stylesheets: for transforming EpiDoc XML to HTML, text or ODF
- EFES: a low-barrier EpiDoc publication platform

In the terminology used in this article, the “EpiDoc Guidelines” and the “EpiDoc Schema” are the descriptive and normative elements of EpiDoc, respectively. The “Reference Stylesheets” (Elliott, Au, et al. 2008–) and “EFES” would be classified as two parts of the “implementation” of the EpiDoc framework. The idea for the VEGEST library arose from observing that EpiDoc provides a reference implementation for their encoding guidelines.

There are two points in which the VEGEST framework aims to emulate EpiDoc. First, EpiDoc’s target was always well-defined: starting from inscriptions, it “expanded to include the publication of papyri and manuscripts [...]”. (EpiDoc Website) Second, EpiDoc provides guidance on how historic principles of typesetting editions correspond to the encoding in XML documents.

The documentation provided by the EpiDoc framework is extensive and useful, just as the norms provided are functional. The overall organisation of normative and descriptive elements conforms to that of the TEI P5 Guidelines: the bulk of EpiDoc’s documentation is in individual XML documents in `guidelines/xml/`. These are exemplary in that they present actual encoding problems, marked up by an `@corresp` attribute on the illustrating `tei-examples:egXML` elements. As in the TEI P5 Guidelines, the general strategy is to provide a schema specification in a dedicated ODD file (`schema/tei-epidoc.xml`), and to write the documentation in a separate directory (`guidelines/xml/`).¹⁴ In both frameworks, the documentation uses `tei:specList/tei:specDesc` elements to refer to the specifications provided in the schemas.

But the way in which the documentation and norms are generated lacks some of the transparency of the integrated ODD workflow used by the TEI Consortium for TEI P5 Guidelines. While the latter provide a `Makefile` that can be used by the open-source program GNU Make to produce required results (such as the documentation or schemas), I was not able to find such a mechanism in EpiDoc.¹⁵

¹⁴In the TEI P5 Guidelines, the schema is specified in the `P5/Source/Specs/` directory, and the documentation is provided in `Source/Guidelines/`.

¹⁵A “Makefile” is essentially a collection of recipes for producing outputs from inputs. E.g., one could specify how to get file “a.html” from a file “a.xml.” Of particular relevance here are the recipes for “p5.xml” and “html-web.” The former recipe defines how to produce the schemas for the TEI P5 Guidelines, and the latter defines how to produce the documentation for the same. Both recipes invoke `ant`, a Java-based build system (with its own file of recipes).

In Elliott, Au, et al. 2008–, the file `README.MD` (section “How to use it”) states that one can configure various parameters in one’s workflow, but does not illustrate what that workflow might look like.

See <https://www.gnu.org/software/make/manual/> (<2025-06-03 Tue>) for documentation

In EpiDoc Sources v9.7, it is the file `guidelines/xml/driver.xml` that ties everything together: it includes the documentation examples along with a “compiled” version of `schema/tei-epidoc.xml`.¹⁶ However, there appears to be no equivalent to the TEI’s `Makefile`.¹⁷ For the reference implementation provided in Elliott, Au, et al. 2008–, the requirements are an XSLT 2.0 processor.¹⁸ In the end, I was not able to assess the reproducibility of the workflow behind the computations that generate the schema and documentation for EpiDoc Sources v9.7 because I could not replicate the workflow. Due to the structural similarity to the TEI P5 Guidelines in terms of the ODD files, I will assume in the following that these transformations would proceed in much the same way as in the case of the TEI P5 Guidelines.

VEGEST is in a different position than EpiDoc because the candidate encoding projects are more diverse. The first substantial difference is that the VEGEST framework targets editions with just a few witnesses (low double digits), whereas EpiDoc focuses on situations “where there is normally only one ancient witness to a text”.¹⁹ Second, VEGEST must consider multilingual witnesses, unlike EpiDoc.²⁰

2.2 VEGEST’s aims

2.2.1 Documentation and norms

As far as documentation and norms are concerned, the VEGEST framework essentially follows the practices of TEI P5 Guidelines and draws lessons from EpiDoc Sources v9.7: the ODD documents are used not only for assembling and defining the individual modules and elements that are to be inherited from TEI P5 Guidelines, but also for illustrating the recommended solutions by application to actual encoding problems. Like EpiDoc Website, VEGEST presents the documentation in a format that will be

on GNU Make.

¹⁶“Compiled” in this context means that all the references to the standard TEI Guidelines have been resolved, see section “How to use it” in `schema/README.txt` of EpiDoc Sources v9.7. The relevant section in `driver.xml` is `~<xi:include href=" ../schema/tei-epidoc.compiled.xml" xpointer="element(/1/2/2/2)"/>~`.

¹⁷The instructions in section “How to use it” in `schema/README.txt` of EpiDoc Sources v9.7 detail a manual process that involves <https://oxgarage.tei-c.org> (which has been superseded by <https://teigarage.tei-c.org/> at the time of writing).

In the file `guidelines/README.txt` of EpiDoc Sources v9.7, a workflow is described that uses the commercial and closed-source Oxygen XML editor (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oxygen_XML_Editor, <2025-06-03 Tue>).

¹⁸See “Technical requirements” in the file `README.MD` in Elliott, Au, et al. 2008–.

¹⁹See the introduction to “Apparatus criticus,” on EpiDoc Website (corresponding to <https://github.com/EpiDoc/Source/blob/v9.7/guidelines/xml/supp-apparatus.xml#L42>).

²⁰EpiDoc Website accounts for translations, but does not, to the best of my knowledge, discuss how to use ancient translations as witnesses for editorial decisions. See <https://epidoc.stoa.org/gl/latest/supp-translation.html>.

familiar to any TEI users.²¹

Since VEGEST has to support both diplomatic and critical editions, the normative and descriptive parts of the VEGEST are modularised. The TEI/ODD specification allows this explicitly through the `@source` attribute on `tei:schemaSpec` (TEI P5 Guidelines: `ref-schemaSpec`; see listing 1).²² In practice, this means that we can formulate a set of rules and their documentation for both kinds of editions that VEGEST schemas define—diplomatic and critical ones. Saving these specifications in a file called `common.odd`, we create two separate documents, `crit.odd` and `dipl.odd`, which inherit the specifications from `common.odd` (see VEGEST schemas, directory `schemas/`, and fig. 2). The definitions for diplomatic and critical editions can add to the included common rules, subtract from them, redefine them, or even include individual elements from other sources.²³

All these techniques are necessary in practice. Elements that have the same function in diplomatic and critical editions will have the same definitions and documentation. These elements can be defined in the common schema. Elements that are specific to each kind of edition, as well as elements that occur in both kinds of editions but have different characteristics in each, are defined in the ODD file corresponding to the edition.

For example, the VEGEST schemas define `tei:ab` as a container for one side of a folio for diplomatic editions, but as the usual, neutral paragraph-like element in critical editions, where the VEGEST schemas suggest its use as a placeholder for including material through `@sameAS` (cf. listing 2). Another example is `tei:body`. Its content model has to be changed for diplomatic editions, yet can be inherited without direct modifications from TEI P5 Guidelines for critical editions.

With the same approach, individual projects can subclass the existing critical and/or diplomatic specifications, adapting the rules through additions, deletions, or replacements. Changes to the vanilla VEGEST schemas are easy to find through a comparison of the schema files or the ODD documents themselves. Any differences between the project-specific and general sets will indicate areas where an adaptation to the software implementation that accompanies the VEGEST (VEGEST library) might be required. Typically, these adaptations will consist of conversions of the new, project-specific markup to the standard VEGEST. This makes it possible to use the entire VEGEST

²¹See, for example, the EpiDoc Website definition of `tei:div` at <https://epidoc.stoa.org/gl/latest/ref-div.html>. The documentation presented on the EpiDoc Website consists of a prose discussion of various aspects of EpiDoc conforming editions, linked to pages that provide the “TEI-style” documentation for online reading. The VEGEST framework does not have a separate document that would correspond to such a description, but follows the TEI P5 Guidelines example of combining both description and norms in ODD documents.

²²In all examples in the text, the prefix `tei:` indicates the TEI namespace (<http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0>). The prefix `tei-examples:` indicates the <http://www.tei-c.org/ns/Examples> namespace.

²³See TEI P5 Guidelines: 23.3.1 for an in-depth discussion.

```

<schemaSpec ident="vegest-critical" start="TEI"
  ↪ source="common.compiled.xml"
  ↪ defaultExceptions="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0 teix:egXML"
  ↪ xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <moduleRef key="tei"/>
  <!-- ... all your changes ... -->
</schemaSpec>

```

Listing 1: Subclassing a `tei:schemaSpec` with `@source`.

```

<elementSpec ident="ab" module="linking" mode="change"
  ↪ xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <gloss>Container for text content and inline markup on a
  ↪ continuous
  material surface (e.g., a page or folio).</gloss>
  <exemplum xml:lang="en">
    <egXML xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/Examples">
      <body xml:lang="sa-Latn">
        <ab>
          <pb n="1a"/><lb n="1a1"/>atha ...
        </ab>
      </body>
    </egXML>
  </exemplum>
</elementSpec>

```

Listing 2: Changing the semantics of `tei:ab` for a diplomatic edition, and providing an example.

toolchain even in adapted projects. A caution is in order here: this strategy works only for such modifications as do not significantly extend the range of the VEGEST. One would not, for example, be able to encode tabular material since there is nothing (at least not at the time of writing) in the VEGEST that would allow for this. One cannot, as it were, “map” tables into the VEGEST’s space. The use cases envisioned in the VEGEST are the adaptation to different analytical frameworks and the possibility of simplifying markup.

One can illustrate this by looking at the treatment of `@type` and `@ana` attributes in VEGEST.²⁴ Using `@ana` attributes allows the encoding to hook into a rich and extendable set of interpretations. Attaching these interpretations to segments of the text (following the recommendations at TEI P5 Guidelines: 17.3) allows the inheritance of sets of attributes and facilitates analysis that can be reused across projects.

The VEGEST schemas allow `@type` (but not `@subtype`) attributes. But because the `@type` values defined for one encoding project are unlikely to be suitable for other projects, the `@type` definition is effectively a shorthand mechanism for the `@ana` attribute. E.g., having `tei:seg[@type="base-text"]` could trigger, upon its conversion to VEGEST conformance, its wrapping in a `tei:quote` element, with the `@source` attribute being inferred from context.

The `@subtype` element is no longer necessary in this scenario, because the equivalence of the value of `@type` to a particular combination of values for `@ana` provides arbitrarily fine-grained distinctions.

2.2.2 Implementation

Guaranteeing the reproducibility of a TEI framework’s implementation—the set of software and programs needed to perform computations on the TEI documents—is more complicated than it is for the documentation and norms of the framework.

In addition to the typical issues associated with software reproducibility, TEI frameworks encounter additional challenges.²⁵ TEI frameworks face the problem that projects will make individual and unforeseeable choices regarding software. In the interest of open experimentation, the question a TEI framework might have to answer is not,

²⁴At the time of writing, this remains a sketch in VEGEST schemas, because no VEGEST specific analytical categories (i.e., `tei:interp` elements) have been added. But the idea is there in principle. See section “VEGEST’s analytical system” in <https://vegest.pages.oeaw.ac.at/vegest-schema/crit-docs.html>, and the description of `tei:interp` in <https://vegest.pages.oeaw.ac.at/vegest-schema/common-docs.html>. See section 4.1.1.

²⁵See Ries, Dalen-Oskam, and Offert 2024 for a recent and succinct overview and discussion of reproducibility in the digital humanities. See Alser et al. 2024 for a fairly current overview of methods to make scientific software available in a manner that increases the reproducibility. (The article focuses on biomedical research, but reflects on several points pertaining to general software reproducibility.) Courtès et al. 2024 discusses the (proposed) solution that VEGEST adopts.

Figure 2: Schema inheritance in the VEGEST framework, TEI to individual projects

“Which software should the projects use?” Rather, it should answer the question, “How can projects use any software they want or need to use?” Since a TEI project is, at its core, a collection of XML files and since XML is designed to make data shareable between applications, it might seem wrong to ask that question of a TEI framework. After all, XML documents don’t care which applications they are fed to and are designed to be universally acceptable data. But the environment that a TEI framework supplies can make things easier or more difficult. The VEGEST framework’s answer to the last question, then, is that it tries to balance adaptability and reproducibility. The overall aim is to create an environment that facilitates both rapid experimentation *and* reproducible research.²⁶

In practice, VEGEST-compliant projects will have multiple but unknown programming language preferences. Even a short list of expected applications is not uniform in terms of the tools required:²⁷ examples of applications include XML transformations

²⁶The institutional setting of VEGEST at the Austrian Academy of Sciences’ Institute for the Cultural and Intellectual History of Asia affords it the luxury of close ties to a fellow institute, the “Austrian Center for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH).” Apart from its extensive research portfolio, the ACDH-CH supplies, given the funding, professional digital humanities expertise and even programming services to projects at other institutes. The VEGEST framework therefore does not need to provide what it would not be able to provide: professional software products aimed at publishing research results or at providing a public interface to the research data.

²⁷Burrows 2023: 283–284 mentions various directions in which digital humanities methods have expanded for historical research. The needs of philology based research show significant overlap with the methods listed there.

(often using XSLT or XQuery), PDF generation (often with \TeX or related systems, or even XSL-fo), machine learning applications (usually created with Python), and systems for handwritten text recognition.

Common challenges that arise in this situation include the lack of standardised installation procedures for software, software dependencies, and pinning versions of software to guarantee both functionality and reproducibility (see Alser et al. 2024: 2530).

There are several ways to tackle this situation. Alser et al. 2024 discusses and compares some popular solutions that “wrap [...] software tools in an isolated software environment using packaging or containerization” (Alser et al. 2024: 2530). These two approaches are differentiated as follows (quoted from Alser et al. 2024: 2530):

- Packaging automates the process of downloading, installing and configuring software tools and dependencies
- Containerization allows software tools and their corresponding dependencies, system tools, system libraries and settings to be distributed and used in a platform-independent manner

To solve issues of software reproducibility, the VEGEST framework proposes the use of GNU Guix, a functional package manager based on the Nix package manager.²⁸ While the categorisation of GNU Guix as a package manager (GNU Guix Developers 2025: 1; Alser et al. 2024: 2532, Table 1) is correct in principle, GNU Guix goes beyond that to provide all the functionality of a container solution as well.²⁹ In practical terms, this means GNU Guix makes it easy to install and run a given piece of software along with all its dependencies. Yet it provides two further functions critical for reproducible and adaptable software: it allows the definition of a bitwise reproducible computational environment, and it can isolate that environment from the host.³⁰

²⁸See GNU Guix Developers 2025: §23.

²⁹See Vila et al. 2024 for a (not DH related) study that treats Docker and GNU Guix as equals in terms of application packaging.

³⁰See GNU Guix Developers 2025: §6.7 for the documentation of `guix time-machine`, which allows for reproducible computational environments. Vila et al. 2024 provides a practical example for the level of bit-wise reproducibility that can be achieved with GNU Guix.

For the container options, see the `guix pack` command GNU Guix Developers 2025: §10.14 which can export (amongst other formats) Docker and SquashFS images.

The command `guix container` allows ad-hoc creation of isolated environments without the trouble of using other containerisation programs. See GNU Guix Developers 2025: §10.14 for its documentation and the warning that this feature is currently experimental.

Several of these commands are used in the examples provided below (section 4.1).

3 Potential reproducibility issues in TEI/XML workflows

But do TEI projects or frameworks suffer any reproducibility issues? If so, what are they, and what are their causes? This section observes that there are three factors that contribute to reproducibility issues: the temporal contingency of software packaging, the dependency on software that is not open-source, and the need for complex software setups to analyse data and conduct experiments.

Reproducible packaging in TEI projects Consider this practical example: the TEI consortium offers a Docker image for building and testing the Guidelines and Stylesheets.³¹ A general idea for building a specific version is shown in listing 3. The approach with a Docker image is very useful. Docker is easy to install on many mainstream operating systems and provides an environment that is largely isolated from the host’s system (see Alser et al. 2024). A single plain-text file, under version control, manages the instructions for creating the Docker image.³² The definitions there declare that the TEI’s development image is to be built from an image that was made for a certain free Linux distribution (Debian Bullseye), and they include a call to the “Advanced Package Tool” (`apt`, starting at `Dockerfile`, line 6) which updates the package repository and installs the required software (`openjdk-17-jdk-headless`, `ant`, etc.). It is this call to an external repository that makes the Docker image inherently non-reproducible: whenever the image is built from scratch, `apt` will update itself from the Debian repositories and fetch whatever version of the software is currently there. That is often the correct behaviour: if one installs programs in an operating system that is in active use, one will usually want the latest version of software packages (including security updates). But for a system that aims at reproducible computational environments, this behaviour is less than ideal. If the image produced at a certain time is lost, it will be impossible to recreate it.³³

Open-source toolchains Another principal cause for reproducibility problems comes into view when we ask whether the full workflow—from encoding to promised result—is truly open-source. Typically, we can pose this question by examining the individual

³¹See the general description of the workflow at https://teic.github.io/Documentation/TCW/testing_and_building.html (<2025-05-27 Tue>). I found no references to Docker or other systems in EpiDoc Sources v9.7.

³²For the TEI’s Docker image, see <https://github.com/TEIC/teidev-docker>. Here, I discuss the `Dockerfile` at revision 7606892c69. The image is published at <https://hub.docker.com/r/teic/teidev-docker>.

³³See Alessandri et al. 2024 for a possible yet cumbersome way around the limitations of Docker’s reproducibility. See Tournier 2021 for an approach that generates reproducible Docker images from within GNU Guix. Whether the latter option would be a viable solution for the problems solved in Alessandri et al. 2024 would need further investigation.

```

mkdir -p /tmp/tei-experiments
cd /tmp/tei-experiments
git clone --depth=1 --branch P5_Release_4.9.0
  ↳ git@github.com:TEIC/TEI.git
git clone --depth=1 --branch v7.58.0
  ↳ git@github.com:TEIC/Stylesheets.git
docker run --rm -it -v ./:/tei -e XSL=/tei/Stylesheets
  ↳ --entrypoint='["bash", "-c", "cd tei/TEI/P5; make -e
  ↳ html-web"]' teic/teidev-docker
ls -lh ./TEI/P5/Guidelines-web/en/html/index.html

```

Listing 3: Obtain (`git clone`) TEI P5 Guidelines and TEI XSLT at specific tags, and use a TEI-provided Docker image to build the HTML version of the Guidelines.

pieces of software used throughout the process; for example, is an open-source XSLT/XQuery processor (such as Saxon HE) sufficient to complete all the tasks? Does the PDF output rely on proprietary features of the XSL-FO processor?³⁴

Problems of software freedom can sometimes appear to be purely theoretical ones, but there is at least one aspect to non-free software workflows that even practical-minded DH researchers should not ignore: non-free software does not lend itself to reproducibility. While any deterministic software, free or not, will produce the same results under the same circumstances, the barriers to obtaining non-free software (including licences, costs, or inaccessibility) are higher than they are for free software.

Technologically complex experimentation A further problem comes into view when one considers the technological expertise that is required to run a TEI-based project. Editing XML documents requires a significant set of skills.³⁵ At the very least, one

³⁴An example: For SARIT, Apache FOP was not sufficient, since it did not support the advanced font features necessary to typeset Sanskrit in Devanāgarī. Cf. also this comment: “Note that you will also need commercial libraries for some steps.” (<https://github.com/ndw/xmlcalabash1>)

To a certain extent, one can also raise questions about the editing environment. Within the TEI/XML encoding community, the Oxygen XML Editor (<https://www.oxygenxml.com/>) is commonly used standard. One should not confuse the XML document with the editor, of course, but if non-free features of the editor are necessary to produce a desired result from the XML documents, reproducibility is unlikely to be satisfactory. To the best of my knowledge, the Oxygen editor can include both free and non-free editions of the Saxon XSLT/XQuery/XML schema processor. So, it would depend on the Oxygen settings whether a certain transformation or operation makes use of non-free (Saxon PE, EE) features. Obviously, this is not a problem of the editor as such but of the software that is packaged together with the editor for the user’s convenience. Doubts about the reproducibility are therefore to be raised about the computing environment rather than the editor.

³⁵VEGEST makes no assumptions about the editor used to encode the documents.

needs a grasp of the basic theory behind XML and XPath and familiarity with the tools for efficiently authoring XML documents, which include a text editor as well as the programs needed to execute XPath queries and to validate a document against a schema. Basic knowledge of either XSLT or XQuery is also highly recommended.

Things become even trickier when researchers start to use more advanced methods of the digital humanities to encode or analyse editions. The complexity of the tools necessary for such tasks can increase rapidly.³⁶ In these situations, updating rapidly developing software can break code that worked with older versions of the software. A method for tracing and managing dependencies between the different software modules is necessary.

We are thus in a situation where TEI projects require a rather wide set of skills to have a chance of success. One focus of the VEGEST is to help TEI projects become sustainable in the long term. Editors should only have to cover the first skill set: how to encode and validate XML editions, and how to use XPath queries to assist them in this.

The VEGEST schemas aim to provide basic prototypes for common needs that go beyond the encoding phase:³⁷

1. High-quality PDF generation via a TEI/XML => T_EX => PDF toolchain.
2. Rapid HTML previews via a TEI/XML => Markdown => HTML toolchain.
3. Refined full-text search that aids editorial decisions

VEGEST are being designed with the awareness that many projects are going to make their own choices about document encoding and tools for utilising the encoded documents, and that these choices will start off as experiments that should allow rapid prototyping. Schema inheritance and extension make for flexible accommodation of different encoding needs for the normative and descriptive parts.

The VEGEST framework provides a set of functions to make use of encoded documents (see VEGEST library). These functions represent the “implementation” of the

³⁶“Advanced methods” here should mean any computation that is not solved by trivial invocation of easily available computer programs. It would include situations in which the researchers need to write small programs or run cutting-edge software that is not easily available. See footnote 27 for a pointer to some examples.

Examples for advanced software suites that are used in TEI projects include Transkribus (not open-source) and eScriptorium (open-source, can run on local workstations). Both can be used for automatic text recognition, and especially handwritten text recognition. A rather complicated piece of software that many TEI users will be familiar with is the *TEI Publisher*, an open-source toolset for publishing TEI editions with minimal programming (see <https://www.e-editiones.org/pages/tei-publisher/documentation/<2025-06-03 Tue>>).

³⁷The focus is currently on PDF generation, since this is the most immediately important output format in the current setting. Full-text search and HTML generation are still in an experimental phase.

VEGEST schemas and are the reason that one can refer to the VEGEST as “implemented guidelines”. These implementations are not intended to be the final word in TEI software. They aim to supply projects with a useful toolset that can be extended quickly and flexibly for rapid prototyping, analysis, and testing: rapid prototyping and analysis allow researchers to run experimental code and queries without a complicated infrastructure, and testing allows them to “pin” results that contribute to the reproducibility of results obtained from running the experiments. Some examples of such functions are discussed in section 4.1.

4 Open and reproducible TEI workflows: VEGEST’s approach

To use a TEI framework such as TEI P5 Guidelines is to subscribe to the conceptual model that it defines. Encoding a verse as a `tei:lg` or a paragraph as a `tei:p` element means that one is classifying a sequence of characters as a verse or a paragraph *as defined by the TEI*. Using the TEI framework not only saves an editor the trouble of fully documenting or defining their understanding of the various classifications that are applied to a text (or simply ignoring these topics and endorsing general unwritten conventions of typesetting), but also moves the edition that is encoded in accordance to a given framework closer to the “FAIR Guiding Principles” (Wilkinson et al. 2016). It is well-understood and has been observed several times how the TEI lend themselves to the FAIR principles.³⁸ In this section, I will discuss primarily how the “FAIR principles for research software” (FAIR4RS) relate to TEI projects and reproducibility.

In order to see how data and the tools to work with the data are not wholly separable, it is worth remembering how a TEI framework or a TEI project satisfies the last two principles (“interoperable” and “reusable”). The TEI’s mechanism of schema customisation (see section 2.2.1, and listing 1) allows an editor to define only the differences of their specific usage of elements versus the general ideas expressed in the overall framework. At the same time, declaring one’s encoding principles as a subclass or variation of a more general set of concepts means that one satisfies the first two sub-principles of the third principle, “to be interoperable:” the edition (or data) will “use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation”, satisfying sub-principle I1, and it will “use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles” themselves, satisfying sub-principle I2 (Wilkinson et al. 2016: Box 2). As observed in Tello et al. 2024: §§8, 10, the `tei:teiHeader` is perfectly adequate for recording detailed information that satisfies all the key points making the data (and its metadata) “reusable.”

Since the ODD documents are themselves TEI/XML documents, they can be tracked

³⁸See Creamer et al. 2021 for the archiving of TEI projects, and Tello et al. 2024: §§5–11 for a clear and recent overview of how the FAIR principles apply to TEI projects.

in basic version control systems.³⁹ Archiving these files, together with a sufficiently detailed narrative about their history, is a significant step towards explainability and reproducibility (see Huskey 2023). Technologically, it is fairly trivial: copy the files somewhere, and ensure against deterioration.⁴⁰ Barring problems around the software needed to read the history or to prove that the files have not changed, this solution is satisfactory.

The FAIR principles were always intended to apply also to “analytical workflows” and non-data elements that were relevant to these workflows. In other words, the FAIR Guiding Principles can be used to assess the software used in a particular workflow.⁴¹ Accordingly, the principles of this application are called the “FAIR Principles for Research Software” (FAIR4RS). These principles are (quoted from FAIR4RS: 5):

- **F:** Software, and its associated metadata, is easy for both humans and machines to find.
- **A:** Software, and its metadata, is retrievable via standardized protocols.
- **I:** Software interoperates with other software by exchanging data and/or metadata, and/or through interaction via application programming interfaces (APIs), described through standards.
- **R:** Software is both usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other software).

³⁹Popular ones are Git (<https://git-scm.com/>) and Mercurial (<https://www.mercurial-scm.org/>). The TEI Consortium tracks its own sources in Git, using the services of <https://github.com/>.

⁴⁰“Fairly trivial” does not mean “trivial.” Securing the survival of digital data poses significant challenges, both in theoretical and practical terms. See Smithies et al. 2019 for an assessment and some practical observations.

⁴¹See the “Introduction” to FAIR4RS for the reception and development of this point. For “analytical workflows” or “pipelines”, see this statement towards the beginning of Wilkinson et al. 2016:

All scholarly digital research objects—from data to analytical pipelines—benefit from application of these principles, since all components of the research process must be available to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and reusability.

In the detailed discussion of the FAIR Guiding Principles, Wilkinson et al. 2016 state:

Analytical workflows, for example, are a critical component of the scholarly ecosystem, and their formal publication is necessary to achieve both transparency and scientific reproducibility. The FAIR principles can equally be applied to these non-data assets, which need to be identified, described, discovered, and reused in much the same manner as data.

In the section “The Principles precede implementation”, Wilkinson et al. 2016 emphasise that no “specific technology, standard, or implementation-solution” is suggested by the FAIR principles. I interpret this as saying that any specific technology must comply to the FAIR principles in order for the workflow to be “FAIR.”

Principle **F** is only partially solved in the exemplar TEI projects that were described above (section 2.1). The framework consisting of (currently) TEI P5 Guidelines and TEI XSLT defines and provides some of the software it needs to operate, and also supplies a Docker recipe (footnote 12) that facilitates the creation of a normalised environment for running the computations that this TEI framework needs. To assess whether the software is “easy to find,” we can note that the software is present either in the repository of the TEI P5 Guidelines or defined through an invocation of Debian’s software package management system (`apt`). However, the “globally unique and persistent identifier” (**F1** in FAIR4RS) is not provided, and there is little to no metadata about the software in the TEI P5 Guidelines repository itself (failing **F4** in FAIR4RS). But since the programs included in the repository and pulled in through the Debian ecosystem are widely in use, their documentation is usually excellent. In other words, TEI frameworks and projects **need** to include the exact version or versions of the software they are intended to run on. A minimum requirement would be for a framework to specify which programs at which version are necessary to generate the documentation and schema files from the ODD sources. Based on the similarity in setup, we can assume that the EpiDoc Sources v9.7 would require the same software. Given the lack of metadata, the same conclusion as for the framework around the TEI P5 Guidelines would have to be drawn for the EpiDoc framework, too.

Principle **A** is satisfied for the TEI P5 Guidelines and TEI XSLT: both the programs installed in the Docker image and the programs present in the source repository are “retrievable via standardized protocols.” Both `git` and `apt` are industry standards, and both build wholly on open-source software.⁴² Since EpiDoc Sources v9.7 do not specify the exact methods to install the expected software, I cannot evaluate the level of conformance to this principle.

Principle **I** is satisfied for both projects in that the majority of output formats produced—XML, HTML, Relax NG, \TeX -like files—can be considered as results of exchanging data (ODD documents or other TEI documents) and metadata (partially included in the relevant sections of the TEI documents and partially defined in the run-time environment of the applications).

The last principle, **R** or that the research software be “usable and reusable” is partially satisfied in the framework around the TEI P5 Guidelines. The Java archives distributed in the source repository, and the packages acquired through the Debian infrastructure, are “described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes” and “includes qualified references to other software” (**R1** and **R2** in FAIR4RS).⁴³ And the

⁴²See https://salsa.debian.org/apt-team/apt/-/blob/main/COPYING?ref_type=heads (<2025-06-04 Wed>) for the licenses involved in `apt` (I am ignoring the servers hosting the software here), and see <https://git-scm.com/about/free-and-open-source> (<2025-06-04 Wed>) for the licensing status of `git`.

⁴³Both Saxon HE and Jing are well documented pieces of software, and both are open-source products

final principle, **R3** or that “the software meets domain-relevant community standards” (FAIR4RS) is likely met given the large and lively TEI user base that routinely uses the software distributed with TEI P5 Guidelines.

There thus seem to be no principle problems that would stand in the way of a good level of “FAIRness” for the basic software infrastructure for TEI frameworks. But there is one snag. In the discussion of “Reusable”, FAIR4RS state: “Note that the general intent of these principles is that software is ‘executable in principle’ - not ‘guaranteed to execute’.” However, a piece of software’s ability to run is contingent on the computing environment that it runs in. If (or rather, because) this environment changes over time, software that is “executable in principle” might come to be software that “was executable some time ago.” This is the problem of reproducibility in software-driven workflows.

Over the last few years, solutions to guarantee better reproducibility have emerged. Rather than targeting individual pieces of software or programming languages (e.g., Python’s `pip`), these attempts target complete computing environments. A very popular solution in this class is Docker,⁴⁴ which allows users to produce an image that can be started like a virtual computer and which contains the software necessary for a given job. The running image (called a container) is largely isolated from the real computer that it is running on. However, the image’s reproducibility is limited by various factors, including the way that software is installed on it initially. There is no guarantee that the software installed when the image is first built will be identical to that installed when the image is built again at a later time — even though the directives for the installation have not changed.⁴⁵

Due to these shortcomings, more rigorous approaches were developed.

The VEGEST framework has found GNU Guix, a system inspired by Nix, to promise a suitable open-source solution for problems of reproducibility.⁴⁶ Much like Docker, GNU Guix defines a complete software environment. That is, we are not only installing this particular version of Xapian in a virtual environment, but we are also defining this environment. But unlike Docker, the GNU Guix definition can be made in such a way that this environment is entirely fixed: storing the current configuration is enough to reproduce the environment in such detail that building any piece of required software will yield identical files. In addition, we can also create an environment in which to run the produced files that is equally well-defined (see listing 4).

Reproducibility in GNU Guix’s model presupposes that the source code of *all the*

that can be cloned through `git` (see <https://github.com/Saxonica/Saxon-HE> and <https://github.com/relaxng/jing-trang>, both accessible on <2025-06-04 Wed>).

⁴⁴See <https://www.docker.com/>, and <https://podman.io/> for a nearly equal set of tools. As discussed above (see section 3, and footnote 32) this is currently the recommended way to work on the TEI P5 Guidelines.

⁴⁵See the discussion of the TEI’s Docker workflow (section 3).

⁴⁶See GNU Guix Developers 2025: §23 for GNU Guix’s debt to Nix.

software needed for a given environment is available—the software needed to build as well as to run the environment and the programs in it. Reproducibility is thus dependent on the long-term availability of the source-code. With solutions discussed in Di Cosmo and Zacchiroli 2017 and Courtès et al. 2024, it is at least possible that open-source DH projects will remain reproducible quite far into the future. The VEGEST framework attempts to make this avenue easily accessible for researchers and editors.

Since this is not the place to give an overview of GNU Guix,⁴⁷ I will here provide some examples that highlight how GNU Guix meets the aims of the VEGEST framework. The intention is to show that basic as well as more involved operations that manipulate TEI-encoded editions can easily be made reproducible by adopting the GNU Guix framework.

4.1 Examples

The following cases are intended to illustrate how the VEGEST framework can be extended to include various pieces of software while remaining reproducible to a high degree. The complexity of the examples ranges from trivial to advanced.⁴⁸ These examples use the same example implementation of transformations as VEGEST library.⁴⁹ While already enabling several transformations that should prove useful for most editorial projects falling within the VEGEST framework’s scope, this implementation is still under active development and far from complete. But it is already certain that it will consist of a chain of transformation steps that combine to form larger transformations.⁵⁰ The VEGEST framework already allows editors to run experiments quickly and to ensure not only that the normative and descriptive aspects of the editorial project are well defined but also that the programs that are necessary to produce the desired output or analysis can be defined more stringently than is currently the case in the other TEI

⁴⁷Courtès et al. 2024 provides a good overview of basic usage of GNU Guix. Accessible entry-level documentation can be found at https://guix.gnu.org/manual/devel/en/html_node/Getting-Started.html.

⁴⁸These examples are given in full at <https://github.com/paddymcall/tei-vegest-reprod-2025>. The listings given below do not always provide the complete code needed to run an example, but are intended to describes the main components.

A case not mentioned here is the author’s own copy of “the TEI framework”, that is, the TEI Guidelines and Stylesheets at a particular version. See <https://github.com/paddymcall/teistuff> (documented at rev 9cc37).

⁴⁹See footnote 50 for the sources of this example implementation.

⁵⁰The design of VEGEST library is closest in spirit to Unix pipelines. While it does not have an equivalent to XProc files, the equivalent of steps specified in an XProc file can be set either on the command line or loaded from project-specific modules. VEGEST library is currently a thin wrapper around a Scheme program (<https://gitlab.oew.ac.at/vegest/guile-stei/>) that implements the various steps (relying also on other software). The reason that VEGEST library and the included Scheme program are not identical is that the former should remain as open as possible to implementations written in other programming languages.

frameworks considered here. Such an approach increases the overall “FAIRness” of TEI projects.

In all of the following examples, reproducibility can be guaranteed by executing the command shown in the example within an appropriate GNU Guix context. Usually, this involves prepending the command with `guix time-machine`, as shown in listing 5. The basic idea is that two sub-commands follow the command `guix`. The first sub-command, `time-machine -C channels.scm`, defines the computing environment as conforming to the version specified in the file `channels.scm` (see listing 4 for an example). These channels are essentially the list of source repositories for GNU Guix itself, with checksums pinning them to a particular revision. This information defines a complete computing environment or an “instance” of GNU Guix.⁵¹ If any of the executable programs for that specific version are not available, GNU Guix uses the recipes in that particular instance of GNU Guix to recreate those programs locally.

```
guix describe -f channels > channels.scm
cat channels.scm
# (list (channel
#       (name 'guix)
#       (url "https://git.savannah.gnu.org/git/guix.git")
#       (branch "master")
#       (commit
#         "9449ab3c2025820d2e6fd679fa7e34832b667ea7")
#       (introduction
#         (make-channel-introduction
#           "9edb3f66fd807b096b48283debdccdfca34bad"
#           (openpgp-fingerprint
#             "BBB0 2DDF 2CEA F6A8 0D1D E643 A2A0 6DF2 A33A
↪ 54FA"))))))
```

Listing 4: Save the GNU Guix channels currently in operation

The second sub-command, `shell`, starts an environment that makes a certain group of packages available. If the `shell` sub-command is invoked without the first sub-command (e.g., `guix shell`), then it defaults to the currently active, local GNU Guix version. When it is preceded by the `time-machine` call, it uses exactly that version of the global GNU Guix package state (or “derivation” in GNU Guix). In practice, one will often call the `shell` sub-command like this: `shell -m manifest.scm --container`. Loading a “manifest” from a file, `manifest.scm`, is much more flexible

⁵¹See https://guix.gnu.org/manual/en/html_node/Replicating-Guix.html (<2025-06-03 Tue>) for details on GNU Guix channels.

than specifying the names of packages as arguments. See listing 9 for an example that makes use of the fact that manifests are actually computer programs.

All the following examples assume that one has issued `guix time-machine -C channels.scm -- shell -m manifest.scm --container --`, and is typing or copying the listed commands in the resulting environment.⁵²

```
# Regular system dependent "ls"
ls
# GNU Guix version of "ls" in an isolated (--container) guix
↪ shell
guix shell --container coreutils-minimal -- ls
# Version of "ls" in a container that is pinned to a
↪ particular version (defined in channels.scm)
guix time-machine -C channels.scm -- shell --container
↪ coreutils-minimal -- ls
```

Listing 5: Calling `ls` (list files) in three ways: the local system’s version, in a GNU Guix container, and in a GNU Guix container running in a fully defined environment.

4.1.1 Extending `@type` to `@ana`

The VEGEST schemas suggest to use `@type` as a shorthand for linking to one or more `tei:interp` values via `@ana` attributes. This approach enables `@type` to stand for an arbitrary collection of interpretations, turning it into a tagging system. The present example illustrates how that mechanism works in principle.⁵³

The (incomplete) TEI document shown in listing 6 has `tei:interp` elements that have an attribute `@corresp` with a value like `type:num4`.⁵⁴ In this hypothetical case, the editor would use the `@type` attribute to assign two interpretations from two different lists of numbers to the same string (the number 4 in a `tei:c` element). To achieve this, one sets its `@type` attribute to `num4`. The command shown in listing 7 transforms the document so that `@ana` attributes with links to the `tei:interp` elements are added to elements with the corresponding `@type`.

The command in listing 7 uses two transformation steps (`-t <step>`). The first expands the `@type` according to the `tei:interp` elements as explained, and the second

⁵²All the examples here can be found in Examples Repository (<https://github.com/paddymcall/tei-reprod/>).

⁵³A complete example that runs in the reproducible computational environment can be found in Examples Repository, (<https://github.com/paddymcall/tei-reprod/tree/main/example-type-ana>).

⁵⁴The VEGEST schemas modify `tei:interp` elements so that they can nest.

```

<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <teiHeader xml:lang="en">
    <encodingDesc>
      <interpGrp xml:id="old-bengali">
        <desc>Numerals from <bibl><ref
          ↪ target="#dimitrov02"/><citedRange>pp59-71</citedRange></bibl></desc>
        <interp xml:id="old-bengali-numerals">
          <interp xml:id="old-bengali-numerals-4">
            ↪ corresp="type:num4">
              <desc>Number 4 as in <bibl><ref
                ↪ target="#dimitrov02"/></bibl>.</desc></interp>
            <interp xml:id="old-bengali-numerals-6">
              ↪ corresp="type:num6">...</interp>
          </interp>
        </interpGrp>
      <interpGrp xml:id="abhisam-script">
        <desc>Numerals from <bibl><ref
          ↪ target="#matsunami98"/><citedRange>147</citedRange></bibl></desc>
        <interp xml:id="abhisam-script-numerals">
          <interp xml:id="abhisam-script-numerals-4">
            ↪ corresp="type:num4">
              <desc>Number 4 as shown in <bibl><ref
                ↪ target="#matsunami98"/></bibl>.</desc></interp>
            <interp xml:id="abhisam-script-numerals-6">
              ↪ corresp="type:num6"/>
          </interp>
        </interpGrp>
      </encodingDesc>
    </teiHeader>
    <text>
      <body xml:lang="sa">
        <!-- These @type attrs will be expanded as @ana linked
          ↪ to the
             tei:interp elements above: -->
        <p><c type="num4">4</c> <c type="num6">6</c></p>
      </body>
    </text>
  </TEI>

```

Listing 6: TEI document linking @:type to tei:interp[@corresp] according to the suggestions in VEGEST schemas

```
run-conversions.scm -t tei-type-to-ana \
                    -t xml-serialise \
                    "<your-tei-document.xml>" > results.xml
```

Listing 7: Expand @type to @ana

(xml-serialise) serialises the results back into XML for further processing.

4.1.2 Transliterating Sanskrit, producing tei:standOff

Sanskrit was and is written in a large number of different scripts. In the present example, the editor is aiming to generate a simplified version of a TEI document’s main textual content (tei:body). This content section should not contain tei:note or tei:app elements, and it should be converted into a romanised transliteration. The command shown in listing 8 transliterates elements with Devanāgarī content (@xml:lang="sa-Deva") to the “International Alphabet of Sanskrit Transliteration (IAST),” a popular romanisation of Sanskrit. In the next step (t tei-standoff) elements such as tei:app and tei:note, which don’t form part of the main content, are moved to a separate section at the end of the document and linked back to their original position. The final step writes everything out to an XML document.

```
run-conversions.scm --xml-lang \
                    -t tei-deva-to-iastr \
                    -t tei-standoff \
                    -t xml-serialise \
                    "<your-tei-document.xml>" > iastr.xml
```

Listing 8: Transliterate Devanāgarī to a Latin transcription, remove notes, and select only tei:body

4.1.3 Formatting of bibliographical references

Fine-grained control of reference formatting is a standard requirement for scholarly editions. This can be achieved with an output-specific solution (Bib(La)TeX for TeX-based documents, for example). In VEGEST library, there is an XML→XML transformation that uses Citeproc (<https://github.com/jgm/citeproc>) to format references. While not as flexible as BibLaTeX, this solution is more general in that the following transformations will not need to format the references any more. In other words, the references will look the same in HTML, plain text, or even TeX files. The general idea

of this transformation is shown in listing 10, and it builds on the definitions in listing 9. This latter listing shows a GNU Guix manifest that is not wholly trivial:⁵⁵

```
(use-modules
 (gnu packages haskell-xyz)
 (guix build-system haskell)
 (guix packages))

(define-public ghc-citeproc-executable
 (package (inherit ghc-citeproc)
  (name "ghc-citeproc-exec")
  (version "0.8.1")
  (build-system haskell-build-system)
  (arguments
   `(#:configure-flags (list "--flags=executable")))))

(concatenate-manifests
 (list
  (specifications->manifest
   '("bash-minimal"
     "pandoc"))
  (packages->manifest
   (list ghc-citeproc-executable))))
```

Listing 9: A GNU Guix manifest that installs a citeproc command (run `guix shell -m manifest.scm -- citeproc --version` to use it)

The input TEI document must have a `tei:listBibl` element with `@corresp` pointing at a BibTeX file. All `tei:bibl` elements in the resulting document will have `@ana` with the value `#csl-rendered-bib`. See listing 11 and in listing 12 for examples of input and output documents, respectively.⁵⁶

4.1.4 PDF generation

A principal goal of the VEGEST framework is to facilitate the generation of print-quality scholarly editions. At present, the VEGEST framework converts TEI/XML documents

⁵⁵See Examples Repository (<https://github.com/paddymcall/tei-reprod/blob/main/manifest.scm>) for the full version.

⁵⁶See Examples Repository (<https://github.com/paddymcall/tei-reprod/tree/main/example-bib-format>) for the complete example, including the BibLaTeX source.

```
run-conversions.scm -t tei-bibl-substitute \
                   -t xml-serialise \
                   "<your-tei.xml>" > results.xml
```

Listing 10: Format bibliographic references in a TEI document with citeproc (use `--csl-style` to specify your own CSL style)

```
<TEI xml:id="bib-test" xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <teiHeader>
    <fileDesc>
      <!-- things missing -->
      <sourceDesc>
        <!-- @corresp points at the bib file -->
        <listBibl corresp="bib.bib"/>
      </sourceDesc>
    </fileDesc>
  </teiHeader>
  <text>
    <body>
      <p>See the explanations in <bibl><ref
        ↪ target="#chue22:_fair4rs"/></bibl>.</p>
      <p><bibl><ref
        ↪ target="#creamer21:_archive_tei_fair"/><citedRange
        unit="page">8</citedRange></bibl> states ... .</p>
      <p><bibl><ref
        ↪ target="#pva_ms"/><citedRange>12a3--6</citedRange></bibl>...</p>
    </body>
  </text>
</TEI>
```

Listing 11: Minimal TEI file that VEGEST library can process citations for. See the results in listing 12.

```

<body xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <p>See the explanations in <bibl
    ↪ ana="#csl-rendered-bib">FAIR4RS</bibl>.</p>
  <p><bibl ana="#csl-rendered-bib">Archiving a TEI project
    ↪ FAIRly 8</bibl> states ... .</p>
  <p><bibl ana="#csl-rendered-bib">B 12a3--6</bibl>...</p>
</body>

```

Listing 12: Results of processing bibliographic references in the document shown in listing 11.

into ConTeXt documents utilising an intermediary and project internal ConTeXt-as-XML format. The ConTeXt documents can then be compiled into a PDF.⁵⁷

In VEGEST-conformant TEI documents, apparatus entries link to the source with @from and @to.⁵⁸ The conversion steps are as shown and commented on in listing 13.⁵⁹

5 Conclusion

This discussion of software reproducibility in TEI frameworks has shown that there is already a solid open-source infrastructure in place that supports common functions of TEI frameworks (documentation, schema generation, document transformation). However, it has also demonstrated the potential for enhancing conformance to the FAIR4RS principles. The adoption of a functional package management tool like GNU Guix in the manner outlined here would improve the reproducibility of these common functions. Such an approach would also benefit experimental and exploratory workflows insofar as it allows researchers to make these reproducible to a high degree. TEI projects using this or a similar approach would therefore conform more closely to the FAIR4RS principles than they would with other approaches, while simultaneously ensuring the longevity of the workflow that drives the project.

⁵⁷ConTeXt is a macro package for \TeX that is useful for automatic processes because there are far fewer conflicts between packages than in the better known macro package, \LaTeX . See <https://github.com/contextgarden/not-so-short-introduction-to-context> and https://wiki.contextgarden.net/Main_Page for more information on ConTeXt.

⁵⁸See the description of the “double end-point attachment method” in TEI P5 Guidelines: §13.2.2, and see the example document in Examples Repository, <https://github.com/paddymcall/tei-reprod/blob/main/example-pdf-format/tei.xml>. The file is a simplified version of an actual editorial project (see McAllister 2022).

⁵⁹See Examples Repository (<https://github.com/paddymcall/tei-reprod/blob/main/example-pdf-format/>) for the complete example that also compiles the PDF.

```

run-conversions.scm \
  --homeurl="https://github.com/paddymcall/..." \
  --homename="TEI Reprod Tests (GitHub repo)" \
  --bib=./bib.bib \
  --standalone \
  -t ana-rm-private # remove all elements with
  ↪ @ana="#private" \
  -t xml-normalize-spaces # normalize spaces, and \
  -t tei-fix-spaces # adjust spaces according to TEI
  ↪ context \
  -t tei-wit-source-to-bibl # Expand @wit reference to
  ↪ full bibliographic reference \
  -t tei-witDetails-absorb # Insert tei:witDetail as
  ↪ notes \
  -t tei-inline-things # Merge text and apparatus \
  -t tei-punctuate-rdgGrps # Separate tei:rdgGrp-s from
  ↪ each other\
  -t context-basics # Basic TEI-XML → ConTeXt-XML\
  -t tei-bibl-substitute # Render bibliographic items \
  -t context-serialise # Serialise ConTeXt-XML to
  ↪ ConTeXt \
  "<your-tei-document.xml>" > tei.tex

```

Listing 13: Convert TEI document to a ConTeXt document. Adding `--show-current` as a transformer at any step will show the data at that point before continuing

Abbreviations and references

Abbreviations

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